

Effectiveness of the Application of Innovative Pedagogical Technology in the Preparation of Athletics for Competitions

F. A. Zaripova¹

¹ Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, Department "Physical Culture", p.f.b.f.d.(PhD), Associate Professor

Abstract:

In athletics, exercises such as walking, running, jumping, and throwing are of particular importance. This article talks about the uniqueness of athletics and preparation for competitions.

Keywords: Athlete, athletics, running, walking, throwing, multisport, healthy lifestyle, versatile person.

INTRODUCTION.

Improving the effectiveness of the management of the training process in the training of highly qualified athletics is considered one of the priority problems in the world of sports, requiring coaches to have in-depth knowledge of pedagogy, sports medicine, sports physiology, sports biochemistry and hygiene, which are closely related to the science of theory and methodology of sports.

In modern high-performance sports, downloads are performed at the limit of biological capabilities. The increase in downloads requires the choice of loads corresponding to the functional state of the organism of athletes. For an athlete with high performance, which is far from straining highly qualified athletes and suffering from any diseases, it is in one training that the means corresponding to individual functional states, their methods of execution, the duration of rest between exercises and trainings of the same physiological direction, the continuous monitoring of the dynamics of adaptation phases in energy systems and their rapid analysis, the formation of long - term to ensure that he would return his record score without.

REFERENCE POSITION...

Athletics is called the "Queen of Sports" and it is one of the most spectacular and popular sports. Today we have collected some interesting information related to its history.:

1. The date of the appearance of athletics dates back to 776 BC. It was then that the first running events at the Olympic Games took place in ancient Greece.
2. In athletics, starting from the bottom was not always the case. Before 1887, the runners before the start were simply waiting for the order. All changed when Sprinter Sherrill followed the kangaroo's action and offered a new posture.
3. At the 1936 Olympic Games in Berlin, Japanese athletes Zhuhai Nisida and Sueo Oe showed the same result and both finished second. But the Japan Sports Federation awarded Oe a bronze medal. Upon returning home, the athletes melted down their medals and made new silver-bronze medals.
4. In the early Olympic Games, the length of the marathon constantly varied from 40 km to 42.75 km. The modern standard of 42 kilometres 195 metres was set as the distance of the 1908 Games in London.
5. The two-time Olympic champion in the distance 10,000 metres, Ethiopian Haile Gebreselassi, had a distinctive appearance during the run: his left arm was pressed against his body and his torso was slightly bent. The athlete himself explains this by the fact that every morning he runs 10 kilometers to school and returns home in the evening, until he presses books in his left hand.
6. New Zealand runner Murray Halberg played rugby as a youngster, but in one of the matches he suffered a serious injury which resulted in paralysis of his left arm. But Murray decided not to throw the sport and started running. Willpower led him to a gold medal in the 5000 metres at the 1960 Olympics in Rome.

MAIN PART.

The relevance of the problem is evidenced by the fact that many of the members of the Uzbek athletics team, namely 84 foyizi, could not show their performance at the level of their functional capabilities at the 2016 XXXI Summer Olympics in Rio de Janeiro.

Purpose:

Improving the effectiveness of the management of the training process in preparing members of the national team for competitions in athletics as a result of the practical implementation of the developed innovativpedagogic technology, based on the laws of adaptation in energy education systems.

Functions:

1. Rapid planning of loading tools, methods of execution and duration of rest in training microcycles based on a quick determination of the functional state of the individual athlete, the reaction of the energo-supply system to the load and the duration of recovery in innovative pedagogical technology.
2. Practical proof of the effectiveness of innovativpedagogic technology developed, which accurately controls the training process of the members of the national team in athletics, with the results of sports shown by athletes in competitions.

Results:

An electrocardiogram was recorded before each session of the highly qualified track and field athletes to determine the athlete's initial functional status.

We determined the training process – the physiological directions of the loads performed and the response reaction of the body of athletes to the load in quick control, gave practical proof of whether the task set in the training was completed, and what tools for performing the task set were recommended for their size, intensity of the method of performing the exercises and the duration of.

The monitoring of the rationality of cardiac activity was carried out with the recording of seismocardiography and its analysis.

In innovative pedagogical technology, we recommended a program to identify and eliminate loose edges in the functional and physical training of an athlete.

Having determined the duration of recovery of the energota'minot system participating in the competition activities up to the super compensation phase after the percussion load, we recommended developing a program to release each athlete in a “sports uniform” position in accuracy up to the hour of the competition.

In each of the highly qualified track and field athletes, we determined the degree of development of the systems by controlling and analyzing the recovery process after the completed loadings of each energy training system, determining the duration of the rest time between exercises and training in the same direction, depending on how long it takes to recover to reach the super compensation phase.

As a result of one or two weeks of monitoring, depending on the chosen type of athlete, we recommended a suitable type, giving information about whether the selected type of athlete is correct, that is, whether he is suitable for his hereditary predisposition.

On the basis of monitoring of adaptation phases in the energy education systems of athletes, functional capabilities, level of mobilization and performance were determined. The severity of physical quality training loadings, age and recovery process were determined, and the next training load, aimed at a specific goal, was determined by rapid diagnosis and accurate control of the training process. As a result, we carried out effective management of the training process through the influence of the load on the athlete's body in order to achieve the planned result towards the program maxad of the functional state of athletes.

In summary,

When we introduce into practice the developed innovative pedagogical technology of accurate control, based on the laws of adaptation in energy systems based on the selection (if incorrectly selected), monitoring of the dynamics of the training process and adaptation phases in energy education systems at training camps, the formation of long-term adaptations from short-term adaptations - to achieve a cumulative effect and we made an opportunity.

The developed innovative pedagogical technology of accurate management of the training process, the effectiveness of which is scientifically based, has been confirmed by the achievements of the members of the national athletics team in practice:

- Margarita Jupikova among teenage girls 1984. 32:40.14 in the 10,000 m, Lyubov Kiryukhina 1987y. the facility set world records in the 600 metres with a 1:25.14 finish.
- Our Athletes Eat. Alekseeva, R. Ivoylova, A. Izmaylovas on sports walking; K. Belyalova, M. Jupikova, L. Kiryukhina, O. Marugina and O. Safans in middle and long distance running; a. Rasskazov onkurash, A. Kirbyatova (Zhuravlyova) held Republican records in the triple jump and in various age groups, one of which was not updated to this day.

LIST OF LITERATURE USED:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017-yil 9-martdagi “O‘zbekiston sportchilarini 2020-yilda Tokio shahrida (Yaponiya) o‘tkaziladigan XXXII Olimpiya o‘yinlari va XVI Paralimpiya o‘yinlariga tayyorlash haqida”gi PF-2821-son Farmoni.
2. Andris E.R., Qudratov R.Q. Yengil atletika. – T., 1998. – 124 s.
3. Волков Л.В. Теория и методика детского и юношеского спорта. – Киев: Олимпийская литература, 2002. – 290 s.
4. Qudratov R.Q. Yengil atletika. Darslik. – Toshkent, 2012. – 367 b.